

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF LEGAL SOCIALIZATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation: *The article highlights the relevance of legal socialization of future teachers based on the needs and demands of society, the content and importance of concepts in inter-disciplinary integration based on the views of scientists. In addition, the components of the improvement of pedagogical mechanisms of legal socialization of future teachers were reflected in the system of educational strategies.*

Keys words: *law, socialization, legal socialization, mechanism, pedagogical mechanism, educational strategy.*

Introduction: The strategy of new Uzbekistan includes the existing political-legal, socio-economic, spiritual-educational reforms in the field of human rights, the formation of human rights culture, Islamic rights and gender issues in the higher education system. development of a continuous education system, introduction of modern methods of forming respect for the law in society;

- "Organization of human rights, women's rights, and children's rights training courses in higher education institutions and personnel, as well as in preschool and general education institutions, academic lyceums and colleges"[1] tasks require the improvement of the systematic regulation of mechanisms for the development of legal consciousness and legal culture in society. One of the important requirements of the development of the society is to educate the young generation who is able to socialize, respects the rights and freedoms of the individual, abides by the rules of the democratic state and society. This requires clarifying the psychological and pedagogical features of the development of professional qualities of pedagogues, who are considered educators of the young generation, on the basis of legal socialization, studying the organizational and pedagogical conditions, and improving the pedagogical mechanisms of legal socialization.

It is worth saying that the work carried out in the reform of the higher education system during the past years is aimed at improving the legal foundations of the higher education system, including "The priority of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan to define directions, raise the process of training highly

qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities, independent thinking to a new level in terms of quality, modernization of higher education, social sphere based on advanced educational technologies and in order to develop economic sectors" [2] adopted in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019 No. PD-5847 ".. .increasing attention to the quality of personnel training in humanitarian and pedagogical directions, revising and improving curriculum and programs in pedagogical education directions and specialties based on advanced foreign experience, this way It is important to start from the higher education system that the students studying in shows that and is a reflection of a consistent policy in raising a healthy generation.

Also, "State educational standard of higher education" dated October 19, 2021. The main provisions. In the Decision No. PD-35-2021 "On approval of the standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan" based on state requirements, regular improvement of the professional competence of pedagogues, the quality of the educational process, educational standards, educational programs, It is provided by such factors as the potential of pedagogues involved in the educational process, the mental potential of learners, technical means of the educational process, educational technologies, and the quality level of educational process management.

Experiences show that, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, said, at the current stage of the development of society, "another main task of the education sector is to train the new generation, the fundamentals of science and one's specialty, which is necessary for today. "It is to educate educated young people", indicates the necessity of forming a generation of modern and broad-minded young people.

In the process of improving the integration of disciplines in the development of education in society, a number of new terms and concepts are entering the science and fields of pedagogy. One such concept is the term "legal socialization", which is a combination of the words "legal" and "socialization". "Legal" is a concept related to law, and it means that it is characteristic of law, such as discipline, discipline. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the category "socialization" not only expresses the meanings of "socializing" and "generalizing", but also means legal activation at a certain level.[4] E. Durkheim connects the concept of "socialization" with the problems of collective consciousness, first of all, the transfer of social norms and traditions from generation to generation.

Most modern sociologists consider socialization as a process of interaction between individuals who develop their own strategies in society and norms and value systems accepted by society. For example, G. Roche defines socialization as "the process by which a person perceives and assimilates socio-cultural elements of his environment, adds them to his personality under the influence of important social factors, and thereby adapts to the social environment" [5,149] describes as legal socialization is the process of assimilation of the system of legal knowledge, values and norms by a person, as a result of which a person successfully adapts to life socially and legally.

"Legal socialization" of a teacher in society is carried out in cooperation with various factors, agents and on the basis of a number of pedagogical mechanisms. It is known that the concept of "mechanism" is an interdisciplinary definition, and its meaning changes depending on the field of application. In scientific and pedagogical studies, the concept of "mechanism" is considered as a set of interrelated elements that determine the order of pedagogical activity.[6] Pedagogical mechanisms are natural changes in the transition from a pedagogical cause (influence) to a pedagogical consequence. Changes that occur in the mind, behavior, and personality of students and teachers under the effect of pedagogical influences: from hearing to understanding and remembering, from knowledge to belief, from skills to habits, from actions and habits to qualities, professional development from skills to professional culture indicates the systematic organization of pedagogical mechanisms.

Pedagogical mechanisms work between cause and effect, pedagogical effect and result. Often, it has a psychological and pedagogical nature, understanding it, relying on it when choosing a pedagogical effect, regulating its "operation" is the most delicate part of pedagogical work. Pedagogical mechanisms due to the conscious and purposeful implementation of human-human relations lie in the systematic structure of professional activity. Based on the systematic structure and activity of professional activity, pedagogical reality in the life of a person and society is represented by the main systematic types of pedagogical phenomena - education, training, teaching, development. Each of them has its own pedagogical facts, laws and mechanisms.

Thus, it can be said that the concept of "mechanism" is activated in pedagogical literature to describe the interrelated system and processes of formation of a certain ability or quality of a person. Like any complex phenomenon of reality, the mechanism has both static and dynamic properties, which represent a set of joint actions, complex specific functionality and multidimensional processes. A.V. Suyushkov made the following additional point to understand the "mechanism concept". Pedagogical

mechanism is an integrated system of multi-level interacting and interdependent processes with a specific beginning and interdependence of results [7].

Based on such interpretations of the concept of legal socialization of future pedagogues, it can be said that the implementation of educational strategies of legal socialization is the possibility of practical implementation of the planned knowledge and skills, developed about the teacher's pedagogical goal and means of achieving it. It is an action oriented to the scientific-theoretical socio-legal result that corresponds to the ideas.

In turn, the mechanism of legal socialization of future teachers is described as a mechanism of pedagogical strategy implementation as follows:

- a set of all elements that ensure the implementation of the functions of the pedagogical system;
- entities and tools that ensure the implementation of a set of measures in the material-technical, organizational, management and social-psychological direction;
- is the activity system of professors and teachers in legal, scientific-pedagogical support of professional and personal development of future teachers [8, 104-109]

In fact, improving the system of pedagogical mechanisms of legal socialization of future teachers is directly related to the study of the current situation in this regard, the search for measures to enrich it, and the determination of targeted measures in the implementation of current plans to eliminate shortcomings. Improving the pedagogical mechanisms of legal socialization of future teachers determines the goal of achieving the following tasks from a scientific-theoretical, legal, and practical point of view.

In our opinion, in the legal socialization of future teachers:

- on its legal basis (the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (adopted and announced on December 10, 1948 by Resolution 217 A (III) of the United Nations General Assembly);
- the Convention on the Rights of the Child (the Convention was adopted in New York on November 20, 1989. It consists of 54 articles);
- Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (consisting of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-837 dated 1.05.2023, Chapter 11, Article 75)
- Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" dated September 23, 2020 (ORQ-637) and presidential decrees and decisions related to the field of education);
- to know the basics of science in his specialty (compulsory, elective block of subjects: pedagogy, field of psychological sciences, etc.);
- to be able to analyze the basics of pedagogy and psychology (methodological, that is, to know the general philosophical laws of education);

- scientific theoretical (knowing the laws of legal knowledge based on the principles of pedagogy and psychology);
- methodical (knowing the levels of designing stages of educational processes in professional activity);
- requires technological knowledge (having the competence to organize educational work in professional activity based on the requirements of pedagogical technology).

Taking into account the above, it can be said that "social pedagogy" is the educational discipline that constitutes the system of social-pedagogical mechanisms of teacher's professional training. The reason: Social pedagogy is a field of pedagogy aimed at studying the laws of socialization of a person, developing and applying technologies of effective methods of social pedagogical activity in order to solve social problems of society. So, as the socialization of a person continues from birth to the end of his life, the subject of "social pedagogy" is the main component for legal socialization, in professional training of a person for the needs of society. The inclusion of this subject in the professional training program of teachers is related to the division of social pedagogy into an independent field of pedagogical knowledge, and its value and importance in modern conditions are determined as follows.

On the basis of the state requirements for social pedagogy, the tasks of improving the organizational and pedagogical conditions of legal socialization of future teachers, clarifying the criteria and indicators for the development of social and legal competence of students were defined as follows:

- filling the content of social pedagogy subjects with socio-legal knowledge;
- to build the process of studying social pedagogy as a process of enriching the experience of the future teacher in solving pedagogical problems of the socio-legal context, and using the technologies of modern educational technologies, contextual education, project-based teaching, and the development of critical thinking;
- development of social and legal competence of future teachers in starting their social and legal activities;

Thus, the overview of pedagogical mechanisms of legal socialization of future pedagogues includes the following features.

- the generality of interrelated elements in ensuring the integrity of legal socialization of future pedagogues;
- as a unique set of inseparable actions aimed at the implementation of legal socialization of future pedagogues;

- the accuracy of defining and developing all the elements and tools that ensure the implementation of a set of measures in the material-technical, organizational, legal and social pedagogical direction for the legal socialization of future pedagogues;

- the synergistic effect of the integration of elements that make up the pedagogical mechanism of legal socialization of future pedagogues;

- the dynamism of the pedagogical mechanism of legal socialization of future pedagogues, the ability of the teacher to practically implement the set of planned actions;

the functional direction of the pedagogical mechanism of legal socialization of future pedagogues, which corresponds to the developed ideas about the pedagogical goal and the means of achieving it, determines the orientation to the legal result.

In conclusion, we emphasize that all the resources used by the teacher to ensure the meaningful learning of students are a specific embodiment of a certain pedagogical concept, educational strategy.

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